

JOURNAL ARTICLE

Bacteriophages are going to save us from bacteria

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Abstract

Bacteriophages or Phages are viruses that specifically infect and kill bacteria, and they have been shown to be effective against antibiotic-resistant bacteria in various studies. Phages are also able to evolve and adapt to the bacteria they infect, allowing them to overcome bacterial resistance. During this process, the phage can exchange genetic material with the bacteria, potentially giving rise to new phage strains that are better able to infect and kill the bacteria. This process of evolution and adaptation allows phages to keep up with the evolution of antibiotic-resistant bacteria. One concern is that the use of phages could lead to the evolution of phage-resistant bacteria. However, this risk can be mitigated by using a cocktail of different phages that target the same bacteria, as this reduces the likelihood of the bacteria developing resistance to all of the phages.

Keywords: Biology, Bacteriophage, Bacterium

1. What are bacteriophages?

Bacteriophages, also referred to as phages, are viruses that attack and reproduce inside of bacteria. These tiny infectious organisms interact in an unusual and fascinating way with their host cells, and they have had a major impact on the diversification and evolution of bacterial populations. We will look at what bacteriophages are, how they function, and how they have been applied to science.

Bacteriophages are present almost everywhere on the planet, including in the human body, water, and soil. They outnumber all other organisms combined as the most prevalent biological species on the planet. Phages can be found in every ecosystem on Earth and are extremely specific, only infecting and replicating within specific types of bacteria.

Bacteriophages have a straightforward structure that consists of a capsid, a protein shell that houses their genetic material. The tail sheath, a flexible layer that surrounds the capsid, aids in the phage's attachment to and injection of genetic material into the bacterial cell. When a phage enters a host cell, its genetic material commandeers the cell's machinery and starts to replicate, eventually creating new phages.

The lytic cycle and the lysogenic cycle are two of the various lifecycle phases that apply to phages. The phage replicates inside the bacterial cell during the lytic cycle before lysing, or bursting, the cell to release new phages. Due to the death of the infected cells, this process can be devastating to the population of host bacteria. On the other hand, during the lysogenic cycle, the phage's genetic material is incorporated into the bacterial genome and can stay there for a long time before becoming active and starting the lytic cycle.

1.1 Parts of a bacteriophage

The bacteriophage's largest and most intricately designed component is its head (1). It includes the virus genetic material, which can either be DNA or RNA. The equipment required for the virus to replicate and infect new host cells is also housed in the head.

The second major part of a bacteriophage is the tail (2). It acts as a means of virus genetic material injection into the bacterium and host cell attachment. A contractile sheath, which the virus uses to anchor itself to the host and inject its DNA, can also be found on the tail.

A bacteriophage is made up of a number of additional components. The tail fibers (3), which are proteins that assist the virus in adhering to the host cell, are one of these. The shape and quantity of the tail fibers can vary, and they are essential for the virus's capacity to infect particular kinds of bacteria.

Another crucial component of a bacteriophage is the baseplate (4). It is a part of the virus that joins the tail to the head and aids in keeping the virus anchored to the host cell. The baseplate also aids in controlling how much genetic material from the virus enters the host cell.

The bacteriophage's outer shell is made up of capsid proteins, which are the last group. These proteins help the virus evade the host's immune system while safeguarding its genetic material.

Figure 1. Atomic structural model of bacteriophage and its parts.

2. How does a bacteriophage infect a bacteria?

The process of a phage infecting a bacterium can be divided into four main stages: attachment, penetration, replication, and release.

2.1 Attachment

A phage must first attach to the bacterial cell in order to infect it. The "tail fibers" or "legs" that protrude from the phage's outer shell are specialized protein structures that are typically used to accomplish this. These elements enable the phage to "land" on the cell by attaching to particular receptors on the surface of the bacterium.

2.2 Penetration

The phage needs to find a way into the cell once it has joined the bacterium. This is frequently done by using an injector that resembles a hypodermic needle and extends from the head of the phage. The bacterial cell wall is pierced by the injector, which then injects the phage's genetic material into the bacterial cell.

Figure 2. Two bacteriophages attached to bacterial cell debris, and two phages have lost their heads.

2.3 Replication

The genetic material of the phage starts to reproduce inside the bacterium using the cell's own machinery. Lysogenic infection or lytic infection may be involved in this process. In lytic infection, the phage's genetic material is reproduced and its proteins are produced, ultimately causing the bacterial cell to be destroyed. The phage's genetic material integrates into the bacterial genome during lysogenic infection and lies dormant until it is activated by an outside stimulus.

2.4 Release

The phage must discover a mechanism to leave the bacteria and infect other cells after it has multiplied to a sufficient quantity. The process of lysis, in which the phage forces the bacterial cell to burst and release the new phages, is commonly used to do this in lytic infection. In lysogenic infection, the genetic material of the phage is passed on to the following generation of bacteria during bacterial reproduction.

3. What happens after the infection?

When a phage infects a bacteria, it injects the bacterium with its genetic material, which can either be DNA or RNA. The bacterium's machinery is subsequently commandeered by the phage's genetic material, which instructs it to make additional phages. Lytic infection is the term for this procedure.

The genetic material of the phage is duplicated during lytic infection, and new phages are put together inside the bacteria. When the bacteria is lysed, or burst, the freshly constructed phages release themselves into the environment. This procedure enables the phages to continue the infection cycle by infecting additional bacteria.

However, in specific circumstances, the phage's genetic material can merge with the bacterial genome and develop into a prophage. This type of infection is called lysogenic. The genetic material of the phage is latent within the bacterium during lysogenic infection, and the bacteria keeps performing its regular functions.

A stressed bacterium, however, may activate the prophage, resulting in lytic infection and the generation of additional phages. The term "lysogenic conversion" refers to this action.

4. How can this help us in the fight against antibiotic resistance?

As bacteria continue to mutate and acquire resistance to the medications used to destroy them, antibiotic resistance is becoming a global concern. As formerly manageable infections become more challenging to control, this process can have negative health effects. The use of bacteriophages, often known as phages, as a potential fix for this issue has gained more attention in recent years.

Phage therapy is one of the main methods that phages can be used to fight antibiotic resistance. In this method, the infection-causing bacteria are specifically targeted and eliminated by administering phages directly to the sick person. In many regions of the world, particularly Eastern Europe and the former Soviet Union, phage therapy has been used for more than a century. In more recent times, it has regained popularity as an alternative to conventional antibiotics, particularly in situations where bacterial infections are multidrug resistant.

Phage use as a strategy to combat antibiotic resistance has a number of potential benefits. The fact that phages can target and kill only the bacteria causing the infection, as opposed to all bacteria in the body as is the case with antibiotics, is one of their main advantages. The balance of healthy bacteria in the body can be upset by the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, but this specificity can help to maintain it. Phages may offer a more long-lasting solution to the issue of antibiotic resistance because they can evolve and adapt to changes in bacterial populations.

Phage use as a strategy to combat antibiotic resistance is not without its difficulties. The absence of regulatory frameworks and standardized protocols for the use of phages in medical settings is a major cause for concern. Additionally, more study is required to determine the ideal circumstances for the use of phage therapy, as well as to better understand its effectiveness and safety.

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